

Supplementary Information

A preliminary study of using greener materials including deep eutectic solvents (DESs) for the cleaning of silver tarnish

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Fig. S 1: Photographs of complexing gels: (a) agar gels (3% w/v) loaded with solutions of 10% w/v saponin, 0.1 M EDDS, 0.1 M sodium glycinate hydrate and 0.1 M sodium thiosulphate respectively; (b) agar gels (3% w/v) loaded with solutions of 20% w/v saponin, 0.5 M EDDS, 0.5 M sodium glycinate hydrate and 0.5 M sodium thiosulphate respectively.

Fig. S 2: Photos of cleaning media applied: (a) mixture of ChCl:U DES and 5 wt.% FeCl₃·6H₂O; (b) FeCl₃·6H₂O:EG DES; (c) NaGly:CA:G:W slurry; (d) NaGly:EG suspension.

Fig. S 3: Schematic illustrations of the application of (a) complexing solutions and (b) oxidative DESs.

Table S 1: Colorimetric values (L^* , a^* , b^* , ΔL^* , Δa^* , Δb^* and ΔE^*_{ab}) measured in SCE mode for the control coupon and those cleaned using the oxidation method, Hagerty cream, and the slurry.

Cleaning method	SCE						
	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔL^*	Δa^*	Δb^*	ΔE^*_{ab}
Control	48.04±0.43	-1.08±0.02	-3.73±0.19				
Hagerty	44.33±0.35	-1.03±0.05	-2.88±0.14	-3.71±0.59	0.05±0.06	0.85±0.24	3.89±0.64
Two-step	81.46±0.62	-0.70±0.07	4.67±0.23	33.42±0.86	0.38±0.08	8.40±0.33	34.52±0.93
Slurry	50.72±0.87	-0.74±0.04	0.15±0.16	2.68±1.09	0.34±0.05	3.88±0.26	4.99±1.12

Fig. S 4: IR spectra of the reference NaGly powder sample, NaGly:EG, cotton stick used to remove the altered tarnishing products for the pure silver coupon and that for the sterling silver coupon.

Fig. S 5 exhibits the EDX elemental maps of Ag, Cl, Na, O and N for a particle that was embedded in the cotton fibers. The right lower corners of all elemental maps overlap (inside of red frames), which may suggest a possible presence of Ag complexation products.

Fig. S 5: EDX elemental maps of Ag, Na, Cl, O and N for a particle embedded in the cotton fibers.